

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

This document describes requirements for medical image data to be processed within SIMCor as part of *WP6 - Data processing for anatomy and function*. First, the document illustrates the specific need for image processing for both use cases, i.e., transaortic valve implantation and pulmonary pressure sensors, to better define the information to be extracted from medical images. The relevant parameters and information obtained via image processing are then visualized using examples. Finally, the document details quality criteria required for the extraction of modelling information.

Table of contents

INTRODUCTION	5
CLINICAL IMAGE MODALITIES EMPLOYED IN SIMCOR.....	6
TRANSCATHETER AORTIC VALVE REPLACEMENT	6
<i>Computed tomography.....</i>	6
<i>Magnetic resonance imaging.....</i>	8
PULMONARY ARTERY PRESSURE SENSOR.....	9
<i>Computed tomography.....</i>	9
<i>Magnetic resonance imaging.....</i>	9
COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY	10
<i>Spatial resolution</i>	10
<i>Temporal resolution.....</i>	10
<i>Field of view</i>	11
<i>Other error sources</i>	12
MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING	13

List of tables

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL RESOLUTION THRESHOLDS FOR IMAGE PROCESSING.	10
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List of figures

FIGURE 1: EXAMPLE OF COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IMAGES BEING USED FOR EVALUATION OF THE PASSAGEWAY FOR THE TAVI DELIVERY SYSTEM. THE ABDOMINAL AORTA AS WELL AS THE LEFT AND RIGHT ILIAC ARTERIES ARE SHOWN. USING APPROPRIATE TOOLS THE DIAMETERS ALONG THE CENTRE LINE OF BOTH POSSIBLE PASSAGEWAYS (LEFT OR RIGHT) CAN BE EVALUATED AUTOMATICALLY.	6
FIGURE 2: EXEMPLARY RECONSTRUCTION OF THE PATIENT-SPECIFIC ANATOMY OF THE LEFT VENTRICLE, THE AORTIC VALVE LEAFLETS AND THE ASCENDING AORTA.....	7
FIGURE 3: EXAMPLE OF THE LEFT VENTRICULAR VOLUME CHANGE OVER TIME (BOTTOM) CALCULATED FROM INSTANTANEOUS MEASUREMENTS OF THE LEFT VENTRICULAR VOLUME (TOP).	7
FIGURE 4: EXAMPLE OF 4D VELOCITY ENCODED MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING DATA. THE METHOD ALLOWS MEASUREMENT OF THE SPATIALLY AND TEMPORALLY RESOLVED PATIENT-SPECIFIC BLOOD FLOW VELOCITY INFORMATION (TOP). FROM THIS INFORMATION, PARAMETERS AS FOR EXAMPLE THE VOLUME FLOW RATE IN THE ASCENDING AORTA (BOTTOM) CAN BE DERIVED.	8
FIGURE 5: EXAMPLE OF THREE RECONSTRUCTIONS OF THE THREE-DIMENSIONAL GEOMETRY OF THE PULMONARY ARTERY OF TWO PIGS AND ONE SHEEP OBTAINED FROM COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IMAGES. IN THE UPPER ROW, ONLY THE IMAGE DATA IS SHOWN. IN THE MIDDLE ROW, THE FINAL RECONSTRUCTION IS SHOWN TOGETHER WITH THE SAME IMAGE SLICE AS IN THE TOP ROW. THE FINAL RECONSTRUCTION IS SHOWN IN THE BOTTOM ROW WITHOUT ANY CONCEALMENT BY THE RAW IMAGE DATA.....	9
FIGURE 6: EFFECT OF THE TEMPORAL RESOLUTION OF CT IMAGING OF THE LEFT VENTRICLE. WHILE THE LEFT VENTRICULAR VOLUME CAN BE ACQUIRED EQUALLY WELL USING 20 OR 10 PHASES PER HEART CYCLE, DIFFERENCES IN THE VOLUME FLOW CHANGE CALCULATED FROM THIS INFORMATION CAN ALREADY BE OBSERVED. FURTHER REDUCTION OF THE TEMPORAL RESOLUTION RESULTS IN FAILURE OF ACCURATE ASSESSMENT OF BOTH THE VENTRICULAR VOLUME AS WELL AS THE VOLUME CHANGE.	11
FIGURE 7: VISUALIZATION OF THE MAXIMUM FIELD OF VIEW THAT CAN BE AVAILABLE FOR RETROSPECTIVE CT DATA (LEFT). HERE, THE COMPLETE ANATOMY OF THE HEART AS WELL AS OF THE PASSAGEWAY FROM THE ILIAC ARTERY TO THE AORTIC VALVE WILL BE VISUALIZED. HOWEVER, THIS USUALLY COMES AT THE COST OF SPATIAL RESOLUTION. ALSO, THOSE IMAGES ARE NOT ACQUIRED FOR MULTIPLE PHASES OF THE HEART CYCLE. ON THE RIGHT SIDE, THE ABSOLUTE MINIMUM FIELD OF VIEW THAT COULD STILL BE USED FOR TAVI DEPLOYMENT SIMULATIONS AND THE IDEAL FIELD OF VIEW ARE SHOWN.	11
FIGURE 8: EXAMPLES OF CT IMAGES WITH A SUFFICIENT CONTRAST AND FIELD OF VIEW FOR RECONSTRUCTION OF THE PULMONARY ARTERY UP TO A LENGTH WHICH IS SUFFICIENT FOR VIRTUAL DEVICE IMPLANTATION (LEFT) AND CT IMAGES, WHERE BOTH THE IMAGE QUALITY AND THE IMAGE'S FIELD OF VIEW ARE NOT SUFFICIENT (RIGHT). HERE, THE WEAK CONTRAST AND NOISY IMAGES PREVENT ACCURATE RECONSTRUCTION OF THE BRANCHING VESSELS. ADDITIONALLY, THE FIELD OF VIEW IS TOO NARROW, SO THAT ONLY A SMALLER PART OF THE RIGHT PULMONARY ARTERY CAN BE SEGMENTED, WHICH IS NOT SUFFICIENTLY LONG FOR VIRTUAL IMPLANTATION OF THE PAPS.	12

FIGURE 9: EXAMPLES OF CT IMAGING ERRORS THAT CAN PREVENT SUCCESSFUL IMAGE PROCESSING. ON THE LEFT SIDE, IRREGULAR ACCUMULATION AND DISTRIBUTION OF CONTRAST AGENTS CAN BE SEEN. THIS PROBLEM PREVENTS THRESHOLD-BASED SEGMENTATION OF ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES. ON THE RIGHT AN EXEMPLARY CT IMAGE THAT WAS TAKEN FROM A PATIENT WITH ATRIAL FIBRILLATION IS SHOWN. HERE, THE IRREGULAR CARDIAC RHYTHM RESULTS IN ERRORS IN THE PROCEDURE AVERAGING IMAGE INFORMATION ACROSS MULTIPLE HEART CYCLES. IN THOSE CASES, MULTIPLE CONTOURS OF ANATOMICAL REGIONS CAN BE OBSERVED..... 12

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AVD	Aortic valve disease
CHA	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin
CT	Computed tomography
ECG	Electrocardiogram
LV	Left ventricle
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
PA	Pulmonary artery
PAPS	Pulmonary artery pressure sensor
TAVI	Transcatheter aortic valve implantation
VEC-MRI	Velocity encoded MRI

Introduction

One major aim of SIMCor is to investigate to what extent numerical simulations can support and enhance development and certification of implantable cardiovascular devices. Here, two use cases were defined. The first use case focuses on the evaluation of heart valve prostheses that can be implanted in a minimally invasive way via cardiac catheterization (i.e., *transcatheter aortic valve implantation*, TAVI). These prostheses are used to replace the native aortic valve in case it is diseased. The second use case deals with *pulmonary artery pressure sensors* (PAPS) that can be implanted into the pulmonary artery, again using catheterization, to monitor pulmonary artery pressure, which is a relevant diagnostic parameter in patients with heart failure.

While TAVI is a relatively young technique, it had a disruptive effect on treatment of aortic stenosis and is already performed more frequently than surgical implantation of aortic valve prostheses¹. The already large number of devices is steadily increasing. In contrast, the first and only PAPS device to date received premarket approval by the US American Food and Drug Administration in 2011².

As both devices are implanted into the cardiovascular system, their requirements regarding safety and efficacy are high. This is associated with large efforts and high costs in development, testing and certification.

Simultaneously to the rapid advancements in the field of implantable cardiovascular devices, numerical methods for simulation of mechanical or hemodynamical properties of the cardiovascular system became increasingly important for academic research. Also, first numerical models used for diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases successfully reached the market and received clearance by regulatory bodies of almost all industrialized nations³. These methods hold the potential to also simulate the interaction between medical devices and the patient-specific cardiovascular system.

To investigate these interactions, the patient-specific cardiovascular system must be described as detailed as possible. Here, most relevant information includes patient-specific anatomy of the aorta, the left ventricular outflow tract, and the aortic valve for the modelling of TAVI procedures, and of the pulmonary artery for modelling of PAPS implantation. Additionally, medical image data also allows, at least to a given extent, to assess patient-specific hemodynamic information on blood flow velocities, and the stroke volumes of the left and right ventricle. The latter are of importance for providing accurate boundary conditions to the numerical simulation models.

In the following section, the evaluation of those anatomical and hemodynamic parameters will be exemplarily described using medical image data from human patients, as well as from pig and sheep animal models, and both data sources are exemplarily shown in this document. Both sheep and pigs are very similar to humans regarding the anatomy of the cardiovascular system and the size of all relevant tissues. Thus, observations regarding required resolutions (temporal or spatial) and image quality are valid for all three species.

¹ <https://www.herzstiftung.de/e-paper/#0> ; page 83

² Ayyadurai P, Alkhawam H, Saad M, Al-Sadawi MA, Shah NN, Kosmas CE, Vittorio TJ. An update on the CardioMEMS pulmonary artery pressure sensor. *Ther Adv Cardiovasc Dis*. 2019 Jan-Dec;13:1753944719826826. doi: 10.1177/1753944719826826. PMID: 30803405; PMCID: PMC6376505.

³ <https://www.heartflow.com/>

Clinical image modalities employed in SIMCor

For assessment of patient-specific anatomies and hemodynamic parameters, medical images will be acquired using either *computed tomography* (CT) or *magnetic resonance imaging* (MRI). Both methods have their individual limitations, accuracy and strengths and will be used for different aspects within SIMCor.

Transcatheter aortic valve replacement

Computed tomography

CT images are routinely acquired prior to any TAVI procedure. Here, angiographic imaging is performed by injecting a contrast agent into the bloodstream, to increase contrast and thus visualization of blood vessels. In general, CT is considered superior for visualization of blood vessels in respect to MRI, as its spatial resolution is usually much higher, and the contrast agent allows for excellent differentiation between bloodstream and tissue⁴.

CT images are used for different aspects of the planning of the TAVI procedure. First, the complete passageway for the TAVI delivery system, usually from the iliac artery at the groin to the aortic valve, can be visualized and measured. This includes diameters and curvatures of vessels, both important parameters to determine whether the TAVI delivery system will safely fit through the passageway (see *Figure 1*). Also, sizing of relevant anatomical structures, e.g., the ascending aorta and the left ventricular outflow tract, will be used to determine the size of the valve prosthesis used during intervention. Additional information used for treatment planning are, among others, the position and orientation of the coronary arteries and the calcification of the aortic valve, as those aspects might prohibit successful TAVI placement. Detailed information on treatment planning can be found, among others, in current guidelines for treatment of aortic valve diseases^{5,6}.

Figure 1: Example of computed tomography images being used for evaluation of the passageway for the TAVI delivery system. The abdominal aorta as well as the left and right iliac arteries are shown. Using appropriate tools the diameters along the centre line of both possible passageways (left or right) can be evaluated automatically.

⁴ Murphy, D. J., Aghayev, A., & Steigner, M. L. (2018). Vascular CT and MRI: a practical guide to imaging protocols. *Insights into imaging*, 9(2), 215–236. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13244-018-0597-2>

⁵ Nishimura RA, Otto CM, Bonow RO, Carabello BA, Erwin JP 3rd, Fleisher LA, Jneid H, Mack MJ, McLeod CJ, O’Gara PT, Rigolin VH, Sundt TM 3rd, Thompson A. 2017 AHA/ACC Focused Update of the 2014 AHA/ACC Guideline for the Management of Patients With Valvular Heart Disease: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Circulation*. 2017 Jun 20;135(25):e1159-e1195. doi: 10.1161/CIR.0000000000000503. Epub 2017 Mar 15. PMID: 28298458.

⁶ Baumgartner H, Falk V, Bax JJ, De Bonis M, Hamm C, Holm PJ, Iung B, Lancellotti P, Lansac E, Rodriguez Muñoz D, Rosenhek R, Sjögren J, Tornos Mas P, Vahanian A, Walther T, Wendler O, Windecker S, Zamorano JL; ESC Scientific Document Group. 2017 ESC/EACTS Guidelines for the management of valvular heart disease. *Eur Heart J*. 2017 Sep 21;38(36):2739-2791. doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/ehx391. PMID: 28886619.

In SIMCor, CT data will also be used to quantify the population statistics of various anatomical structures, as for example the population distribution of diameters of the left ventricular outflow tract and the ascending aorta, or the minimal opening area of the stenosed aortic valve during systole. However, the main use of this medical image modality is the reconstruction of the patient-specific anatomy of the left ventricular volume, the aortic valve leaflets, and the aorta (see *Figure 2*). This three-dimensional anatomical information is vital for various aspects. First, if dynamic CT information is present, where the heartbeat is captured at multiple time points, segmentation of the left ventricle can be performed for each of these time points. This allows measurement of the left ventricular end-systolic and end-diastolic volume, which are relevant parameters for diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases and allow estimation of hemodynamic parameters, e.g., stroke volume and cardiac output. Additionally, from the left ventricular volume per time point the complete volume flow waveform can be calculated (see *Figure 3*).

Figure 2: Exemplary reconstruction of the patient-specific anatomy of the left ventricle, the aortic valve leaflets and the ascending aorta.

Information on the three-dimensional patient-specific anatomy will be required for device implantation simulations (WP8) and device effect simulations (WP9), as well as for generation of virtual cohorts including virtual three-dimensional geometries (WP7). Here, the anatomies, together with additional tissue- and device-related information (e.g., mechanical properties), are vital inputs for the numerical models. Another important aspect is represented by hemodynamic information, e.g., the volume flow rate in the aorta.

Figure 3: Example of the left ventricular volume change over time (bottom) calculated from instantaneous measurements of the left ventricular volume (top).

Magnetic resonance imaging

While this imaging technique is widely used in clinical routine, it is neither part of the routine assessment nor of the treatment planning protocols for TAVI patients. One reason for this is that CT allows a more accurate assessment of the heart and the large vessel size. However, MRI is widely used for other clinical applications and allows measurements that cannot be obtained with CT or are obtained at a much lower accuracy. Here, examples are measurement of the left and right ventricular myocardium mass or investigation of dynamic processes within the heart. One major feature of MRI, that is especially relevant for numerical modelling approaches, is its ability to measure patient-specific blood flow velocity information in a temporally and spatially resolved manner. This technique, commonly described as *velocity encoded MRI* (VEC-MRI) has found wide appreciation in cardiovascular research but also in clinical application⁷.

The possibility to measure three-dimensional blood flow velocity vectors in a completely non-invasive manner allows for excellent personalization of patient-specific models for in-silico diagnosis or treatment planning⁸. Even if this information is not used directly for parametrization of numerical models (e.g., as boundary condition), it enables corroboration of those models.

In SIMCor, this type of information derived from medical image data will be utilized for validation of models, for definition of boundary conditions of models, but also for the generation of synthetic cohorts, which will not only include basic demographic and anatomic features, but also hemodynamic information. Examples of this information are patient-specific velocity profiles measured in the left ventricular outflow tract, or the main pulmonary artery or volume flow curves in those vessels (*Figure 4*).

Figure 4: Example of 4D velocity encoded magnetic resonance imaging data. The method allows measurement of the spatially and temporally resolved patient-specific blood flow velocity information (top). From this information, parameters as for example the volume flow rate in the ascending aorta (bottom) can be derived.

⁷ Dyverfeldt P, Bissell M, Barker AJ, Bolger AF, Carlhäll CJ, Ebberts T, Francios CJ, Frydrychowicz A, Geiger J, Giese D, Hope MD, Kilner PJ, Kozerke S, Myerson S, Neubauer S, Wieben O, Markl M. 4D flow cardiovascular magnetic resonance consensus statement. *J Cardiovasc Magn Reson*. 2015 Aug 10;17(1):72. doi: 10.1186/s12968-015-0174-5. PMID: 26257141; PMCID: PMC4530492.

⁸ Belén Casas García (2018); Dissertation; Towards Personalized Models of the Cardiovascular System Using 4D Flow MRI. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1253246/FULLTEXT02.pdf>

Pulmonary artery pressure sensor

For the PAPS, the same medical imaging modalities will be available and will be mainly used for the same purposes, even though the anatomy of interest is different (i.e., the pulmonary artery rather than the aorta). Thus, to be succinct, only examples of usage of both image modalities are presented.

Computed tomography

CT data used for the PAPS use case will be mainly processed to assess anatomic parameters and the respective three-dimensional patient-specific anatomies (i.e., the pulmonary artery). As the PAPS can be implanted into the left and right pulmonary artery, more geometric measurements describing the vessel and implantation zone are necessary. These are, among others, lengths and diameters of the respective vessel segments, angles under which vessels branch from the main arteries, cross-sectional areas of branching vessels as well as the curvature of vessel segments. Exemplary three-dimensional models of the pulmonary artery of two pigs and one sheep are presented in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: Example of three reconstructions of the three-dimensional geometry of the pulmonary artery of two pigs and one sheep obtained from computed tomography images. In the upper row, only the image data is shown. In the middle row, the final reconstruction is shown together with the same image slice as in the top row. The final reconstruction is shown in the bottom row without any concealment by the raw image data.

Magnetic resonance imaging

While CT data is preferred for assessment of the patient-specific anatomy, there are also MRI sequences suitable for this task. However, the spatial resolution of MRI is usually lower than CT one. Thus, relevant measurements, especially reconstruction of the narrow branching vessel, will be associated with higher degrees of uncertainty. However, for assessment of patient-specific haemodynamics, MRI data will be a vital tool. Like for the TAVI use case, VEC-MRI sequences can be used to determine volume flow rates and patient-specific velocity profiles in the pulmonary artery⁹. This image modality will thus be useful for the assessment of the flow rate distribution in the left and right pulmonary artery.

⁹ Wehrum T, Hagenlocher P, Lodemann T, Vach W, Dragonu I, Hennemuth A, von Zur Mühlen C, Stuplich J, Ngo BT, Harloff A. Age dependence of pulmonary artery blood flow measured by 4D flow cardiovascular magnetic resonance: results of a population-based study. *J Cardiovasc Magn Reson*. 2016 May 31;18(1):31. doi: 10.1186/s12968-016-0252-3. PMID: 27245203; PMCID: PMC4888740.

Quality criteria for clinical image data

Computed tomography

Spatial resolution

In general, higher spatial resolutions will lead to less uncertainty in sizing of anatomical structures and the reconstructed patient-specific three-dimensional geometries. Overall, voxel resolutions of $0.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ are preferred and ideal for reconstruction of the overall anatomy. High resolution is required, especially for segmentation of the intricate leaflets of the aortic valve. However, aortic valve leaflets could also be reconstructed from less resolved data with voxel resolutions of 0.8 to 1.0 mm in each direction¹⁰. Still, the lower the resolution, the higher the risk that the aortic valve cannot be reconstructed in a satisfactory manner. As CT images are usually averaged across multiple (3 to 8) heart cycles, coarse resolutions result in a rather noisy visualization of the aortic valve leaflets. The larger structures of the left ventricle and the aorta, however, can even be segmented using voxel sizes of up to 2 mm in each direction¹¹.

Temporal resolution

In SIMCor, retrospective CT image data will be used. This data was acquired for various clinical indications, e.g., treatment planning of TAVI procedures, or investigation of myocardial and coronary artery perfusion. Thus, the data will vary regarding its temporal resolution. Also, as CT uses ionizing radiation, one relevant aspect of CT diagnostic is to reduce the overall radiation energy. While for evaluation of coronary perfusion the diastole is the most vital time point, other investigation will focus on the systolic phase. These phases are identified using *electrocardiograms* (ECG) measured during the CT procedure. ECG information will also be used for triggering and averaging the images across multiple heart cycles. The anatomy of all relevant structures can be derived from any time point. However, information on systole and diastole is the minimum required to accurately calculate general hemodynamic parameters, e.g., stroke volume and thus the cardiac output. In theory, the relevant anatomical information for device implantation simulation can be derived from any time point throughout the heart cycle. However, information on diastole and systole are also preferred to assess the maximum variation of relevant sizes, e.g., the aortic or pulmonary artery diameter.

For assessment of more complex hemodynamic parameters, e.g., the volume change of the left ventricle, at least 10 time points are required (*Figure 6*). Requirements for spatial and temporal resolution are summarized in *Table 1*.

Parameter	Ideal	Moderate	Poor
Spatial resolution (voxel size X x Y x Z mm ³)	$\leq 0.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$	$\leq 1.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0$	$> 1.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0^*$
Temporal resolution (phases per heartbeat)	≥ 20	≥ 10	< 10
*image data with poor resolution might still be used for reconstruction of the left ventricle and aorta, however the intricate structures of the aortic valve leaflets cannot reliably be reconstructed using such coarse resolutions.			

Table 1: Overview of spatial and temporal resolution thresholds for image processing.

¹⁰ Franke B, Weese J, Waechter-Stehle I, Brüning J, Kuehne T, Goubergrits L. Towards improving the accuracy of aortic transvalvular pressure gradients: rethinking Bernoulli. *Med Biol Eng Comput.* 2020 Aug;58(8):1667-1679. doi: 10.1007/s11517-020-02186-w. Epub 2020 May 26. PMID: 32451697; PMCID: PMC7340661.

¹¹ Hellmeier, F., Nordmeyer, S., Yevtushenko, P., Bruening, J., Berger, F., Kuehne, T., Goubergrits, L. and Kelm, M. (2018), Hemodynamic Evaluation of a Biological and Mechanical Aortic Valve Prosthesis Using Patient-Specific MRI-Based CFD. *Artificial Organs*, 42: 49-57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aor.12955>

Figure 6: Effect of the temporal resolution of CT imaging of the left ventricle. While the left ventricular volume can be acquired equally well using 20 or 10 phases per heart cycle, differences in the volume flow change calculated from this information can already be observed. Further reduction of the temporal resolution results in failure of accurate assessment of both the ventricular volume as well as the volume change.

Field of view

The field of view is another essential aspect for the CT image data to be used in SIMCor. Usually, the field of view is directly linked to the spatial resolution, as a limited number of pixels can be acquired per slice (e.g., 512 rows x 512 columns). Thus, a limited field of view is favourable in terms of spatial resolution. However, the field of view must contain all information required for the image reconstruction. For the TAVI use case, the minimal field of view for virtual device implantation must include at least the left ventricular outflow tract, the aortic valve and the ascending aorta. However, the ideal field of view will also include the complete left ventricle as well as the descending aorta and aortic arch (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Visualization of the maximum field of view that can be available for retrospective CT data (left). Here, the complete anatomy of the heart as well as of the passageway from the iliac artery to the aortic valve will be visualized. However, this usually comes at the cost of spatial resolution. Also, those images are not acquired for multiple phases of the heart cycle. On the right side, the absolute minimum field of view that could still be used for TAVI deployment simulations and the ideal field of view are shown.

For the PAPS use case, the required field of view must include the main, the left and the right pulmonary artery. As the PAPS will be implanted into the left or right pulmonary artery, these vessels must be completely visible, to allow reconstruction of a sufficient segment that allows virtual implantation of the PAPS (*Figure 8*).

Figure 8: Examples of CT images with a sufficient contrast and field of view for reconstruction of the pulmonary artery up to a length which is sufficient for virtual device implantation (left) and CT images, where both the image quality and the image's field of view are not sufficient (right). Here, the weak contrast and noisy images prevent accurate reconstruction of the branching vessels. Additionally, the field of view is too narrow, so that only a smaller part of the right pulmonary artery can be segmented, which is not sufficiently long for virtual implantation of the PAPS.

Other error sources

Even though spatial and temporal resolution and the field of view are sufficient for processing of image data, there are other error sources that can prevent successful or at least accurate reconstruction of the patient-specific anatomy. Often, those aspects cannot be easily monitored automatically but can easily be discerned by manual inspection of CT images. Common problems are related to uneven distribution of contrast agents in vessels, resulting in noisy images and strong Hounsfield Unit gradients. Another common problem results from atrial fibrillation during CT image acquisition. As CT images are often generated by averaging the image signal across multiple heart cycles, these heart cycles must be registered with each other. This registration is performed using ECG. However, in patients with atrial fibrillation, the heart rate is not periodic, resulting in failures of this averaging procedure. Examples for these two error sources are shown in *Figure 9*.

Figure 9: Examples of CT imaging errors that can prevent successful image processing. On the left side, irregular accumulation and distribution of contrast agents can be seen. This problem prevents threshold-based segmentation of anatomical structures. On the right an exemplary CT image that was taken from a patient with atrial fibrillation is shown. Here, the irregular cardiac rhythm results in errors in the procedure averaging image information across multiple heart cycles. In those cases, multiple contours of anatomical regions can be observed.

Magnetic resonance imaging

Only a subset of the patient datasets to be used in SIMCor will also include MRI data. While MRI data can provide additional information regarding the patient-specific haemodynamics, they are not strongly required. Thus, requirements for MRI data are not that strict.

Various approaches for assessment of blood flow velocity vectors using velocity encoded MRI exist. In general, acquisition of the four-dimensional velocity information (three orientations, time) can be performed for a three-dimensional volume (4D-3D). Thus, for each three-dimensional voxel in the field of view, temporally resolved information of the three-dimensional velocity vector will be available. While this approach provides the best insight into the patient-specific haemodynamics, it is associated with relatively long measurement times. Thus, only planar acquisition of the four-dimensional velocity is often performed (4D-2D). Here, a measurement plane is defined in which all three velocity components are measured during the whole heart cycle. An even faster approach is the measurement of only the velocity component perpendicular to a measurement plane (2D-2D). While this approach still allows measurement of volume flow rates, it fails at assessment of complex flow patterns and underestimates the real maximum velocity. Thus, four dimensional measurements are to be preferred.

With respect to the spatial resolution, voxel sizes between 2 and 4 mm in each direction allow good estimation of patient-specific velocity profiles and volume flow rates, as both vessels, the aorta, and the pulmonary artery, are rather small. As the temporal resolution of VEC MRI is usually larger than that of CT imaging procedures (commonly > 20 phases per heartbeat are acquired), no limitations are to be expected in this regard.